

The influence of stress mindset on health among genocide adult survivors in Rwanda: A moderated mediation model of perceived stress and coping style

Pièrre IYAMUREMYE^{1*}, Callixte NZARIKURIKIZA ²

¹ School of Psychology, Department of Applied Psychology, Guizhou Normal University, Guiyang, China.

² College of Teacher Education, Department of education and Developmental Psychology, Zhejiang Normal University, P.R.China.

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***Corresponding Author:**
Pièrre IYAMUREMYE

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Evidence indicates that holding particular stress mindsets has favorable insinuations for peoples' health as well as survivors under stress. Previous studies have depicted the relationship between Stress mindset (SMM) and Physical well-being. However, they are no studies that have investigated the relationship between SMM and Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), even less is revealed on the side of mediating and moderating processes based on this relationship. The present study surveyed the relationship between SMM and PTSD, and tested the mediating impact of perceived stress and the moderating impact of coping strategies that included approach and avoidant coping. A total of 1000 participants including college genocide survivors and graduated ones who are ranged between 26-35 and 36-45 years old from The Northern province of Rwanda completed an online questionnaire regarding SMM, PSS, Brief cope, and PTSD. Findings showed that SMM was negatively related to genocide survivors' PTSD symptoms, and perceived stress mediated this relationship. The direct relation between SMM and PTSD, including the relationship between SMM and perceived stress were both moderated by Approach and avoidant coping style. The relationships between SMM and PTSD symptoms, as well as between SMM and PSS were stronger in genocide survivors who experience higher levels of coping style. These results contribute to a comprehensive understanding of when and in which ways SMM may be associated with genocide survivors' PTSD symptoms, and enrich new outlook for the enhancement of genocide survivor's mental health 27 years after the 1994 Genocide against Tutsi in Rwanda.

Keywords: Stress mindsets; Coping; Perceived stress; PTSD; Genocide survivors.

Introduction

The Tutsi Genocide was the most traumatic and stressful man-made event in Rwandan history. The Tutsi genocide claimed the lives of roughly 1 million people who were killed in one of the worst genocides of the 20th century within a period of 3 months and lasted from **April, 1994 to July, 1994**, (**Republic of Rwanda, 2014**). This bad event led to a great number of survivors and many children lost most, if not all, of their family members, and took on the responsibility of caring and providing for other child survivors, and the necessity of adjusting to new and difficult life circumstances, (**Schaal & Elbert, 2006**).

More crucially, referring to different previous studies, we find that life long time even twenty seven years (27) after Genocide against Tutsi, the high prevalence of stress and mental health problems among genocide survivors in Rwanda is still a serious concern. Recent study revealed that thousands of genocide survivors of the 1994 Rwandan Genocide against the Tutsi were not only exposed to a remarkable severe forms of violence that led them to mental health problems, but also many of these survivors took on the responsibility of caring and providing for other child survivors, (**Lauren C. Ng, Naphtal Ahishakiye, 2015**).

Moreover, it is clear that this situation caused survivors having various mindsets on stress, and Stress mindset is considered to be a new concept in the field of psychology that has the potential to enhance our understanding of stress and its impact on our health. The stress mindset is depicted as the belief that stress has enhancing (**stress-is enhancing mindset**) or debilitating (**stress-is-debilitating mindset**) consequences for outcomes such as productivity and well-being among individuals (**Crum, Salovey, & Achor, 2013**). Stress on the other hand is defined as the tension that occurs when one perceives an external event as exceeding the capacity to cope afforded by one's personal resources, or well-being (**Lazarus Rs, et., al. 1978; Lovallo, 2015**).

Some survivors still experience mental diseases like Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (**PTSD**) symptoms diagnoses, in Rwanda range from **29% to 79%** (**Neugebauer et al., 2009; Schaal, Dusingizemungu, Jacob, & Elbert, 2011**), with those who were between the ages of 11 and 20 during the genocide being at the highest risk for PTSD (**Munyandamutsa, Mahoro Nkubamugisha, Gex-Fabry, & Eytan, 2012**). Another survey about **223,500** people sought consultation in public hospitals for mental health related treatment in 2018, found that **10 %** of the above were new patients while **35.6 %** are survivors of the 1994 genocide against the Tutsi, generally **35%** of Genocide survivors have mental health problems, (**Dr .Iyamuremye J, 2018**). Nevertheless, no study to date has examined the relationship between the stress mindset and Post -Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) in this group of survivors, much more on this association is still unrealized.

PostTraumaticStressDisorder(PTSD)isdefinedas a severely debilitating disease that can occur in people who have experienced or witnessed natural disasters, serious accidents, terrorist accidents, the sudden death of a loved one, the death of a parent, war, genocide, rape and other violent physical attacks or other lifethreatening ev

ents (posttraumatic stress disorder). It is also defined as a mental disorder that can develop after exposure to unusual threats or terrible events. Its main characteristics are reexperience, avoiding traumatic memory and being vigilant or overvigilant against the feeling of constant threat (Maercker A, Brewin CR, Bryant RA, et al.2013). In most population and genocide survivors Posttraumatic stress disorder includes four symptom clusters according to DSM-5, namely, hyperarousal, persistent reexperiencing of the trauma, avoidance of trauma-related stimuli, and negative alterations in cognitions and mood. Empirical findings have further characterized PTSD symptomatology, as summarized next. PTSD is a heterogeneous disorder, and there are several subtypes of it depending on the situation. One is characterized by hyper arousal, and a second by dissociation, numbness, and physiological unresponsiveness, accounting for approximately 70 and 30% of occurrences, respectively ,(Lanius RA,Bluhm R 2006&Loewenstein RJ,2010).

Hypothesis 1: SMM is negatively associated with PTSD symptoms. That is, as long as genocide survivors experience more stress mindsets, they will have higher levels of PTSD symptoms.

Though SMM can increase the levels of PTSD symptoms, the underlying mediating (i.e., how SMM affects PTSD) and moderating (i.e., when the association is enhanced or buffered) mechanisms remain unknown. Exploring its mediating and moderating mechanisms would provide guidance for our further understanding of how and when SMM predicts PTSD symptoms. To address these gaps, the present study suggested a complex conceptual model to further examine the mechanisms underlying the relationship between SMM and PTSD among genocide survivors. We firstly, surveyed the mediating effect of perceived stress on the relationship between SMM and PTSD. Secondly, we investigated the moderating effect of coping (approach and avoidant) on the relationship between SMM and PTSD via the mediation of perceived stress.

The Mediating Function of perceived stress.

In our daily life situation, perceived stress is the feelings or thoughts that an individual has about how much stress they are under or experience at a given point in time or over a given time period. Perceived stress includes feelings about the uncontrollability and unpredictability of one's life, how often one has to deal with irritating hassles, how much change is appearing in one's life, and confidence in one's capability to deal with problems or difficulties. It is not measuring the types or frequencies of stressful events which have happened to a person, but rather how an individual feels about the general stressfulness of their life and their ability to handle such stress. Individuals may suffer similar negative life events but appraise the impact or severity of these to different extents as a result of factors such as personality, coping resources, and support. In this way, perceived stress reflects the interaction between an individual and their environment which they appraise as threatening or overwhelming their resources in a way which will affect their daily life situation (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). The perception that stress affects one's health is conceptually differ from the amount and the level of stress an individual experiences; indeed, one could report experiencing very little stress but still believe it to have a great impact on their health (eg; Genocide survivors).In addition, the perception of stress

affecting health may have the impact on health outcomes differently than the amount or the severity of stress. Theoretical work supports the concept that the perception that stress affects one's health may impact future health outcomes. Particularly, the transactional model of stress and coping provides critical insight into the appraisal of stress and the available resources for how to handle and manage the stress (Wenzel, Glanz, & Lerman, 2002). Referring to the literature reviewed above, we suggested the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2: Perceived stress will mediate the relationship between SMM and PTSD symptoms among genocide survivors. Particularly, when survivors involve in more SMMs, they will face higher perceived stress, which in turn will be related to higher levels of PTSD symptoms.

The Moderating Function of coping style (approach and avoidant)

Though SMM may be significantly associated with PTSD through perceived stress, it looks impossible that all genocide survivors will experience an equal level of PTSD symptoms when experiencing SMMs.

Therefore, it is important to examine some potential variables that can moderate the direct and indirect relations between SMM and PTSD symptoms. Approach and avoidant may be the key moderating variables.

In the Stress, Appraisal and Coping theory (Lazarus & Folkman 1984), coping is defined as behavioral and cognitive strategies that individuals use to handle undesirable/stressful situations. It is postulated that coping resources can mediate the adverse effect of stress on health outcomes (Lazarus & Folkman 1984). As fact, internal or external environment demands are stressors on which any individuals including genocide survivors are required to fight to sustain a comfortable life situation. In the occurrence of imbalance between the individual potential resources and the environmental stressors, people experience the reduction of physical and PTSD symptoms and forced to utilize effort to restore balance (Lazarus & Cohen, 1997).

Approach is also known as Problem-focused coping strategies.

Problem-focused coping strategies are found when the individual tries to take a direct approach to handle their problem and reducing their mental discomfort or stress. Planning the steps to get from point A to point B; they are having nightmares, they want to reduce them, what needs to be done to make that happen. In many cases, problem-focused coping is used when the individual has more control over their specific stressors and can directly change their situation (Cherewick, 2016). Problem-focused coping is also an active approach trying to overcome the problem causing distress, for example, setting up a nutrition plan to lose weight, (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). However, in Rwanda's case, many of the stressors are uncontrollable – parents' death leading to survivor or orphan status, for example and actively trying to solve an unsolvable problem can actually increase stress and mental health problems. The individual will have thoughts such as, "I should have done something, I could have stopped this", that will add guilt to health problems and stress of the event itself. Problem-focused coping can be useful if it is used correctly. Exposure therapy – i.e. visiting genocide

acceptance rather than repression (Mbabazi, 2016). Thought Field Therapy – thinking about specific traumatic events and tapping on specific body points to release negative energy – reduced child genocide survivors’ perceived PTSD symptoms from 72% to 18% and their clinical symptoms from 100% to 6% (Sakai, 2010).

Avoidant coping strategies

Avoidance-focused coping refers to the general behavior of removing oneself mentally or even physically from the source of stress rather than actively coping with it or finding a solution. For example, **increasing sleep hours** or **avoiding thinking about the problem** (Kohn, Hay & Legere, 1994). Avoidance is always considered as a negative coping strategies, which are related to more physical symptoms, (Billings, D.W., Folkman, et., al.2000). but it depends on how the strategies are implemented. Previous research investigated several coping strategies regarding their effectiveness in reducing the negative effect of stressors on PTSD symptoms. The results in the present study suggested an avoidance coping style is associated with higher PTSD symptoms , in contrast to more active approaches who face the stressor and/or its related emotions like approach coping. Behavioral disengagement in the form of avoiding the stressor was shown to cause a lack of control during the stressful event as well as a lack of will to confront the stressor which is associated with poor adjustment (Dijkstra & Homan, 2016). Positive avoidance, in Rwanda, has manifested itself primarily in the form of individual education. A study of orphaned survivors showed that, of 61 orphaned children, 70% had returned to school by 2002 and that, by 2008, 90% had finished primary school, 43.75% had finished secondary school, and 27.08% went on to university. The article then goes on saying, “Education may be beneficial because it may offer hope and the possibility of a brighter future to orphaned heads of households (OHH). In addition, going to school is one of the primary normative experiences for children, and for OHH who are suddenly thrust into the adult roles of caregiver and breadwinner, education may offer an opportunity for success in a developmentally appropriate everyday role, as well as providing access to concerned adults” (Lauren,2015). So, for children who lost their parents and were thrown into adulthood overnight, education provides an outlet through which they are able to avoid their new responsibilities and return to normalcy, even if for only a few hours a day. Negative avoidance can also be found when people repress the memories, and stress, live as if the experience simply didn’t happen as a way of avoiding the strong and painful emotions associated with that experience. Relying on the preceded discussion, we proposed the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3: Approach and Avoidant coping will moderate the direct and indirect relations between SMM and PTSD symptoms via perceived stress as a mediator. Especially, the direct and indirect relations between SMM and PTSD symptoms will be much stronger for the genocide survivors with higher levels of coping strategies.

The Present Study

The current study aimed to examine the relationship between SMM and PTSD symptoms in genocide

survivors. Further, the mechanisms underlying this association were explored. Firstly, we examined whether SMM is negatively associated with PTSD. Secondly, we tested the mediating role of perceived stress in the relation between SMM and PTSD. Thirdly, we tested whether the direct and indirect relations between SMM and PTSD through perceived stress would be moderated by coping style (**approach and avoidant**). Therefore, we proposed a moderated mediation model (See Fig.1).

Fig.1. The proposed moderated mediation model.

Note: X: Stress Mindset, Mi: Perceived Stress, W: Coping style (Approach & Avoidant), Y: PTS

Materials and methods

Participants

Participants were recruited by convenient sampling from one Private University, **Institute of Applied Sciences (INES)** located in the Northern Province of Rwanda and corresponding local community. The study included also those genocide survivors who are abroad owing to different reasons. All participants should have been experienced Rwanda's 1994 genocide **against Tutsi**. A total of 1115 genocide survivors voluntarily participated in the survey and got some incentives. After removing the participants whose answers and status did not meet our survey condition, those who met the criteria and provided answers to all items in the questionnaire, finally the sample included **1000** participants. Among these, **671(67.1 %)** of the samples were "Male", **329(32.90%)** of the samples were female; **705(70.50 %)** of the samples are aged **26 to 35(52.9%)**; **295(29.50%)** are in the range of 36 to 45years old; **529(52.90)** lost both parents; **238(23.80 %)** lost their fathers; **198(19.80 %)** lost their mothers;**35(3.5%)** still have both parents. For living environment, **238(23.8%)** were orphan-headed households; **245(24.50%)** were from adopted families; **206(20.6%)** were mothers who got married and headed families; **283(28.30%)** were father who got married and headed families. Further, more than **861(86.10%)** were graduated from university while more than **489(48.90 %)** are students; from the distribution of religion, most of the people are "Catholic", and the proportion is **481(48.10%)**; the proportion of Protestant is **312(31.20%)**.

Measures

The stress mindset (SMM)

It was assessed using **stress mindset measure** by (**Crum et al. 2013**). This consists of eight (**8**) items and intends to measure the mindset individuals hold about stress. The items ask about the general attitude individuals hold about the impact of stress. The measure includes four positively stated items and four negatively stated items, which were answered on a 5-point-Likert scale (0 = *Strongly Disagree*; 4 = *Strongly Agree*).

The Perceived Stress Scale from (PSS)

It is the most widely used psychological instrument with ten (**10**) items for measuring the perception of stress. It is a measure of **the degree to which situations in one's life are appraised as stressful**. Items were designed to tap how unpredictable, uncontrollable, and overloaded respondents find their lives. The scale also includes a number of direct queries about **current levels of experienced stress**. (**Cohen et al.1983**). The questions in this scale ask you about your feelings and thoughts **during the last month**. In each case the questions was answered with **0 = Never 1 = Almost Never 2 = Sometimes 3 = Fairly Often 4 = Very Often**.

Coping Strategies

They were measured by the Brief COPE which is a **28-items** self-reported questionnaire, made up of

fourteen sub-scales (self-distraction, active coping, denial, substance use, use of **emotional support**, use of **instrumental support**, behavioral disengagement, venting, positive reframing, planning, humor, acceptance, religion, and self-blame). Each item was on a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from 0 (“not at all”) to 3 (“a lot”) by (Carver 1997).

Post-traumatic stress disorder

The PTSD was measured by PTSD-8 which is a short PTSD scale derived from the HTQ. The PTSD-8 consists of eight items rated on a four-point Likert scale (1 not at all, to 4 a lot). A total symptom severity score can be calculated. A cutoff score indicating possible PTSD can also be obtained by the following criterion: at least one item within each PTSD symptom cluster (**intrusion, avoidance, hyper vigilance**) with a score of 3 or higher. In the present study, internal consistency measured by Cronbach’s alpha for the total scale was satisfactory (Hansen M et al.2010).

Procedure & ethics.

The current study was approved by the review boards of the University, **Institute of Applied Sciences (INES)** located in the Northern Province of Rwanda and the Committee of the local government community .This study was carried out within 6 months as a period of time. In order to not cause any excess psychological stress concerning a very sensitive subject matter, I interviewed genocide survivors who willingly volunteered to share their stories and who had established relatively stable lives post-genocide, and whose English level was good. I focused my research on interviewing institutions about their role in providing care for traumatized and stressed survivors and from reading testimonies accessible either online or in print. All participants completed the online survey on their own devices being freely able to choose the time point and place. To ensure confidentiality, participant names were removed from interviews prior to data entry, and the questionnaire identified only by a number code, and all others involved in the project were told that no information would be released about individual participants. Letters of explanation and consent forms were sent to genocide survivors via email or link sharing and return the forms by using the same way. Participants were selected as genocide survivors from a wide range of geographical areas including Universities and other parts of the country especially in northern province, even abroad and to have roughly unequal numbers of males and females, male number was higher than female because as different researches show that female are more emotional and somehow difficult for them to speak out what they faced. Participants were contacted and asked if they wanted to give testimony of their genocide experiences. After being asked to fill out questions about their information about demographics, gender, age, education, as well as occupation, participants were asked to answer questions, mostly in multiple-choice style about stress mindset, perceived stress level and coping strategies, and PTSD. The completion of the study took at least 15 to 20 minutes.

Data Analysis.

All analyses were performed using **IBM SPSS statistics (version 26) predictive analytics software** and the PROCESS macro for SPSS statistics. Missing cases were removed from the data set. First, descriptive analysis was done to calculate the means, standard deviations and correlations between the study variables. Correlation analysis was performed to examine the association between the variables stress mindset, coping, perceived stress, and PTSD. In order to test the hypothesis, research model illustrated in **Figure 2**, the bootstrap mediation and moderation procedure by **Hayes (2018)**, regression-based PROCESS macro for SPSS was used. Model 59 of this macro allows for carrying out serial multiple mediator and moderators analyses. The statistical in **Figure 1** shows that in a model with one mediator, the total effect of X on Y can be partitioned into a network of direct and indirect constituents. One “**pathway**” runs directly between X and Y and acts for the direct effect. The other effect is indirect and it runs through another three separate pathways. Based on ordinary least squares (OLS) regression, PROCESS provides estimates of parameters for all the direct components within the pathways, including the direct effect of X on Y . In addition to these parameters, PROCESS generates bootstrap confidence intervals to estimate the indirect effect(s) of X on Y . The independent variable stress mindset, the dependent variable PTSD and one mediator perceived stress was analyzed.

The PROCESS analysis is restricted to only one dependent variable at a time. Therefore, separate analyses were to be carried out for each of the outcome variables in the model. This ensured that the same standard errors and confidence intervals would be generated each time the program was run, with the Y variable as the only changing factor. An additional advantage of this fixed seed is that it enhances the replicability of the research (**Hayes, 2018**).

Mediation analyses was conducted to assess whether one potential mediator which was perceived stress mediated **the association** between stress mindset and PTSD. **Pearson correlation** was used, (**Algina, J., & Keselman, H. J. 1999**). A *p*-value of **0.05** was used to determine the statistical significance of the parameters for *direct* effects between the different pairs of antecedent and consequent variables captured in the model. For the *indirect* effects, the confidence level of the bootstrap confidence intervals was set to **95% and 1000** bootstrap samples were used. If zero does not occur between the lower limit (**LBCI**) and the upper limit (**UBCI**) of the interval, then we can conclude (**with 95% confidence**) that the true indirect effect is not zero (**that is, there is mediation**).

Results

Preliminary analysis

The discriminant validity was test by the comparison between the square roots of the average variance extracted (AVE) and the correlation coefficients of any variables. The results showed that all AVE values were greater than **0.5**, and the square roots of AVE were all greater than the correlation coefficients of any variables, thus indicating good discriminant validity of these scales (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2006).

The test for the multicollinearity of the model found that all the **VIF(Variance Inflation Factor)** values in the model are less than **5**, which means that there is no collinearity problem; and the Durbin-Watson value is near the number **2**, thus indicating that the model does not have autocorrelation. There is no correlation between the sample data, the model is good.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics and intercorrelations between variables (n = 1000)

Variables	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.Stress Mindset	1.492	0.766	1							
2.Perceived Stress	22.14	5.020	-0.250**	1						
3.Approach coping value	32.63	7.483	0.368**	-0.183**	1					
4.Avoidant coping value	23.03	5.850	-0.363**	0.467**	0.014	1				
5.PTSD	25.63	3.215	-0.420**	0.493**	-0.275**	0.454**	1			
6.Intrusion	13.13	1.952	-0.335**	0.386**	-0.203**	0.393**	0.812**	1		
7.Avoidance	6.25	1.333	-0.272**	0.391**	-0.179**	0.321**	0.679**	0.293**	1	
8.Hypervigilance	6.25	1.200	-0.280**	0.257**	-0.209**	0.220**	0.605**	0.224**	0.231**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**p < 0.01.PTSD=Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

Testing for Mediating Effect

In Hypothesis 2, we anticipated that Perceived stress would mediate the relation between SMM and PTSD. We used Model 4 of the PROCESS macro to test this hypothesis after controlling for gender, age, genocide survivors, living environment, higher education level and only occupation (Hayes, 2017). As Table 2 and Fig 3 shows SMM was negatively associated with Perceived stress ($\beta = -1.507$, $t = -7.436$, $p = 0.000 < 0.01$), and Perceived stress was positively linked to PTSD ($\beta = 0.263$, $t = 15.307$, $p = 0.000 < 0.01$).

Fig.2. Mediation effect of perceived stress between SMM & PTSD

Furthermore, when the mediator (Perceived stress) was included in the model, SMM was also negatively related to PTSD ($\beta = -1.273$, $t = -11.300$, $p = 0.000 < 0.01$). This proposed that Perceived stress partially mediated the relation between SMM and PTSD. The bootstrap results also indicated that the conditional indirect effect of SMM on PTSD through Perceived stress was significant (indirect effect = -0.396 , Boot SE = 0.0706 , Boot 95% LLCI = $[-0.5399]$ and Boot UPCI = $[-0.2622]$). The mediation effect accounted for 15.4% of the total effect.

Table 2

Testing the mediation effects of Perceived stress in the relation between SMM & PTSD.

Predictors(IV)	Model 1(DV:PTSD)			Model 2(DV:Perceived stress)			Model 3(DV:PTSD)		
	β	SE	t	β	SE	t	β	SE	t
Gender	0.802	0.352	2.276	-0.097	0.212	-0.457	-0.308	0.191	-1.609**
Age	0.961	0.372	2.582	0.652	0.224	2.913	0.400	0.202	1.976
Genocide survivors	-0.297	0.177	-1.679	-0.096	0.107	-0.898	-0.018	0.096	-0.182
Living environment	-0.200	0.129	-1.555	0.036	0.077	0.463	0.089	0.070	1.269
Highest education level	-0.389	0.456	-0.854	0.471	0.274	1.717	0.573	0.247	2.323
Occupation	0.696	0.204	3.407	0.384	0.123	3.121	0.200	0.111	1.802
Stress Mindset	-1.507	0.203	-7.436**	-1.670	0.122	-13.699**	-1.273	0.113	-11.300**
Perceived Stress							0.263	0.017	15.307**
R^2	0.088			0.196			0.350		
F	13.695***			34.525***			66,602***		

p < 0.01, *p < 0.000. IV=Independent Variable, DV=Dependent variable, PTSD=Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder.

We found that both the total effect and the direct effect are significant.

And 95% BootCI of the indirect effect of Perceived Stress does not include the number 0, indicating that the mediation effect is significant.

Here we can also see that the mediated model involves three models, the control variables in **model 1** are Gender, Age, genocide survivors status, Living environment, Highest education level, Occupation, the independent variable is Stress Mindset, and the dependent variable is Perceived Stress. The **R value** of the model is **0.088**, which means that the model can explain the **8.8%** change in Perceived Stress. **The model passed the F test (FFT 13.695, pause 0.000 < 0.05)**, which

shows that the model is meaningful. The regression coefficient of Stress Mindset is

-1.507, which means that Stress Mindset has a significant negative effect on Perceived Stress.

The formula of the model is: $\text{Perceived Stress} = 23.251 + 0.802 * \text{Gender} + 0.961 * \text{Age} - 0.297 * \text{genocide survivors status} - 0.200 * \text{Living environment}$

$0.389 * \text{Highest education level} + 0.696 * \text{occupation} + 1.507 * \text{Stress Mindset}$; **model 2**. The control variables in model 2 are Gender, Age, genocide survivors status, Living environment, Highest education level, Occupation, and the independent variable is Stress Mindset. **Model 3** we

added Perceived Stress on the basis of model 2, and the dependent variable of the model is: PTSD.

As can be seen from model 2, the value of model **R** is **0.196**, which means that the independent variable can explain **19.6%** of the change in PTSD. The model passed the F test, which indicated that the model was meaningful, and the regression coefficient of Stress Mindset was

($\beta = -1.670$), which meant that Stress Mindset had a significant negative effect on PTSD.

The male formula of the model is: $\text{PTSD} = 24.858 - 0.097 * \text{Gender} + 0.652 * \text{Age}$

$0.096 * \text{genocide survivors status} + 0.036 * \text{Living environment} + 0.471 * \text{Highest education level} + 0.384 * \text{Occupation} - 1.670 * \text{Stress Mindset}$

For model 3: after adding Perceived Stress to model 2, the change of F value is significant

($p < 0.05$), which means that the addition of Perceived Stress has explanatory significance to the model. In addition, the value of R increases from **0.196** to **0.350**, which means that Perceived

Stress can produce **15.4% interpretation of PTSD**. Specifically, the regression coefficient of Perceived Stress is **0.263**, and it is significant ($t = 15.307$), which means that Perceived Stress has a significant positive effect on PTSD.

Testing for Moderated Mediation

We used Model 59 of the PROCESS macro for SPSS to test moderated mediation after controlling for gender, age, genocide survivors, living environment, higher education level and only occupation (Hayes, 2017). As illustrated in Table 3, the product (interaction term) of SMM and Approach coping had a significant predictive effect on PTSD ($\beta = -0.087$, $t = -4.559$, $p < 0.000$, and on Perceived stress ($\beta = -0.012$, $t = -1.090$, $p < 0.000$). In addition, the product (interaction term) of Perceived stress and Approach coping had significant effect on PTSD ($\beta = 0.003$, $t = 1.743$, $p < 0.05$).

Furthermore, as it is also illustrated in Table 4 the product (interaction term) of SMM and Avoidant coping had a significant predictive effect on PTSD ($\beta = 0.123$, $t = 4.742$, $p < 0.000$, and on Perceived stress ($\beta = 0.101$, $t = -2.066$,

$p < 0.000$). In addition, the product (interaction term) of Perceived stress and Avoidant coping had significant effect on PTSD ($\beta = 0.015$, $t = 6.821$, $p < 0.05$).

It's shown that the effect of X (Stress Mindset) on Y (PTSD) is significant, indicating that the moderation effect of Approach and Avoidant coping value exists.

The results suggested that the relationships between SMM and PTSD, and between SMM and Perceived stress were both moderated by Approach and Avoidant coping. To better interpret the moderating effects of Approach and Avoidant coping, we examined the simple plot effects of both SMM on PTSD and SMM on Perceived stress, separately for high and low levels of Approach (+1 SD below the mean and -1 SD above the mean) (see Figs. 2 and 3). Simple slope tests showed that the association between SMM and PTSD was stronger for genocide survivors with high Approach coping ($\beta_{\text{simple}} = -1.639$, $t = -11.803$, $p < 0.000$) than for genocide survivors with low Approach coping ($\beta_{\text{simple}} = -1.059$, $t = -6.031$, $p < 0.000$). Furthermore, for the association between SMM and PTSD with high avoidant coping ($\beta_{\text{simple}} = -0.889$, $t = -5.191$, $p < 0.000$) than for genocide survivors with low Avoidant coping ($\beta_{\text{simple}} = -1.316$, $t = -9.427$, $p < 0.000$). Similarly, the association between SMM and Perceived stress was stronger for genocide survivors with high Approach coping ($\beta_{\text{simple}} = -1.657$, $t = -7.177$, $p < 0.000$) than for genocide survivors with low Approach coping ($\beta_{\text{simple}} = -0.356$, $t = -1.218$, $p < 0.224$). Besides, for the association between SMM and PTSD with high avoidant coping ($\beta_{\text{simple}} = -0.403$, $t = 1.467$, $p < 0.000$) than for genocide survivors with low Avoidant coping ($\beta_{\text{simple}} = -1.037$, $t = -4.632$, $p < 0.000$).

Furthermore, the bias-corrected bootstrap analyses indicated that the indirect effect of SMM on PTSD via Perceived stress was moderated by Approach and Avoidant coping. For genocide survivors with low levels of Approach coping, the indirect effect of SMM on PTSD via Perceived stress was -0.083 , Boot SE = 0.082 , Boot 95% CI = $[-0.50, 0.079]$. In contrast, the indirect effect for genocide survivors with high levels of Approach coping was -0.453 , Boot SE = 0.080 , Boot 95% CI = $[-0.610, -0.303]$. On the other hand for genocide survivors with low levels of Avoidant coping, the indirect effect of SMM on PTSD via Perceived stress was -0.0160 , Boot SE = 0.049 , Boot 95% CI = $[-0.264, 0.076]$. In contrast, the indirect effect for genocide survivors with high levels of Avoidant coping was 0.132 , Boot SE = 0.090 , Boot 95% CI = $[-0.043, 0.321]$. In sum, these results indicated that Approach and Avoidant coping moderated the relationship between SMM and PTSD via Perceived stress.

Fig.3. There is a mediating effect of the moderation

Note: **X: Stress Mindset, Mi: Perceived Stress, W: Coping style (Approach & Avoidant),**

Y: PTSD

Table 3
Testing the moderated mediation effects of SMM on PTSD (Approach as a moderator)

Predictors(IV)	Model1(DV:Perceived stress)			Model 2(DV:PTSD)		
	β	SE	t	β	SE	t
Gender	0.691	0.348	1.987*	-0.323	0.190	1.701
Age	0.946	0.367	2.578	0.393	0.201	1.959
Genocide survivors	-0.239	0.175	1.363	-0.005	0.095	-0.050
Living environment	-0.175	0.127	-1.374	0.085	0.069	1.225
Highest education level	-0.439	0.449	-0.978	0.575	0.245	2.345*
Occupation	0.670	0.201	3.325**	0.192	0.111	1.734
Stress Mindset	1.831	0.711	2.574*	-0.685	0.397	1.726
Approach coping value	0.056	0.035	1.610	-0.084	0.043	1.951
SMM*Approachcoping	-0.087	0.019	-4.559**	-0.012	0.011	-1.090**
Perceived Stress				0.165	0.054	3.073**
PSS*Approach coping				0.003	0.002	1.743**
R^2	0.116			0.361		
F	50.710***			14.407***		

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.000. IV=Independent Variable, DV=Dependent Variable, PTSD=Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder.

Table 4

Table.4. Testing the moderated mediation effects of SMM on PTSD (Avoidant as a moderator)

Predictors(IV)	Model1(DV:Perceived stress)			Model 2(DV:PTSD)		
	β	SE	t	β	SE	t
Gender	0.924	0.318	2.903**	-0.194	0.184	-1.055
Age	0.569	0.336	1.692	0.343	0.194	1.768
Genocide survivors	-0.267	0.160	-1.675	-0.036	0.092	-0.392
Living environment	-0.184	0.116	-1.590	0.084	0.067	1.253
Highest education level	0.029	0.411	0.072	0.596	0.237	2.519*
Occupation	0.462	0.185	2.500*	0.223	0.107	2.086*
Stress Mindset	-3.150	0.589	-5.348**	-2.609	0.395	-6.614**
Avoidant coping value	0.094	0.063	0.482	-0.297	0.067	-4.428**
SMM \times Avoidant coping	0.123	0.026	4.742**	0.066	0.017	3.866**
Perceived Stress				-0.101	0.049	-2.066*
PSS \times Avoidant coping				0.015	0.002	6.821**
R^2	0.262			0.407		
F	39.114***			61.573***		

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.000$. IV=Independent Variable, DV=Dependent Variable, PTSD=Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder.

Fig. 4. Approach coping moderated the relationship between Stress Mindset and PTSD. Note: PTSD = Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder.

From the simple slope table and simple slope chart, we found that the **p value** of the moderator variable Approach coping value is **less than 0.05** at different levels, indicating that when the moderator variable is at different levels, the independent variable Stress Mindset has a **significant negative effect on the dependent variable PTSD**, and the influence range is different. When the moderator variable Approach coping value is at a high level, the independent variable Stress Mindset has a greater negative effect on the dependent variable PTSD.

Fig. 5. Avoidant coping moderated the relationship between Stress Mindset and PTSD. Note: PTSD = Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder.

From the simple slope table and simple slope chart, we found that the **p value** of the moderator variable Avoidant coping value is less than 0.05 at different levels, indicating that when the moderator variable is at different levels, the independent variable Stress Mindset has a **significant negative effect on the dependent variable PTSD**, and the influence range is different. When the moderator variable Avoidant coping value is at a low level, the independent variable Stress Mindset has a greater negative effect on the dependent variable PTSD (**B= 1.316**).

Discussion

In current study, we investigated the association between SMM and PTSD in genocide survivors, and constructed a moderated mediation model to examine whether perceived stress mediated the association between SMM and PTSD, and whether Coping strategies (Approach and Avoidant) acted as moderating roles in the direct and indirect relationships between SMM and PTSD. To our knowledge, this is the first study to explore the relationship between SMM and PTSD symptoms, as well as the mechanisms underlying this association with genocide survivors as participants. Results showed that SMM related to PTSD not only directly, but also indirectly through the mediator of Perceived stress. Furthermore, Approach and Avoidant played a moderating role in the relationships between SMM and PTSD, as well as between SMM and Perceived stress.

Consistent with our hypothesis, the present study discovered that SMM was negatively correlated with genocide' PTSD symptoms, even after controlling for demographics. Consequently, survivors engaging in more stress mindsets are more likely to acquire perceived stress and show higher levels of PTSD symptoms especially those between 36-45 years and above according to our findings from the present study. The main reason is that those who are from 36 years old and above by the moment, they were about 11 years old during the 1994 Genocide against Tutsi. So they are able to remember and make flashbacks of what happened in that time.

The Mediating Function of Perceived stress.

As predicted, perceived stress partially mediated the relationship between SMM and PTSD. Therefore, Perceived stress was not only an outcome of SMM, but also a predictor of PTSD. Specifically, for the first path of the mediation process, we found that SMM was negatively linked to Perceived stress. This finding coincides with the prior studies, suggesting that negative stress beliefs, in particular, have been found to predict negative affect (Daniels et al., 2006), somatic symptoms (Laferton et al., 2018), and perceived stress (Fischer et al., 2016). Genocide survivors who have more stress mindsets are more likely to face higher perceived stress, that can even lead them to PTSD symptoms.

From the simple slope table and simple slope chart, it is found that the **p value** of the moderators variables Approach and Avoidant coping value is **less than 0.05** at both the high level and the average level, indicating that at the independent variable Stress Mindset has a significant negative effect on the dependent variable Perceived Stress at both the high level and the average level, and the influence range is different. When the moderators variable Approach and avoidant coping value are at a high level, the independent variable Stress Mindset has a greater negative effect on the dependent variable Perceived Stress (**B= 1.657**).

For the second stage of the mediation link, this study indicated that perceived stress was positively related to PTSD,

As expected, perceived stress partially mediated the relationship between stress mindset and PTSD symptoms in genocide survivors. A lower level of mindset may result in higher levels of perceived stress and further lead to higher level of PTSD symptoms. Perceived stress (as a risk factor) reduces the positive impact of stress mindset (as a positive factor) on PTSD symptoms. These findings suggested that we could reduce and prevent PTSD symptoms of genocide survivors by enhancing the level of mindset and/or decreasing level of perceived stress. (Dweck & Leggett 1988) have shown that the way individuals think about the fixedness or malleability of intelligence regulates how they react in challenging situations. Individuals believing that intelligence is flexible or increasable are more likely to view difficult tasks as a possibility of learning, growth and experience low stress.

The Moderating Function of Approach coping

Our study further found that Approach could moderate the associations between SMM and PTSD, as well as between SMM and Perceived stress. Specifically, both the relation between SMM and PTSD and the relation between SMM and Perceived stress got stronger when genocide survivors had higher levels of Approach coping strategies. Our findings are congruent with the study of (Arias & Pape, 1999; Dirkzwager, Bramsen, & van der Ploeg, 2003; Solomon, Mikulincer, & Flum, 1988; Stein et al., 2005),

That is, lesser use of adaptive problem solving strategies (i.e., engagement or active problem coping) and greater use maladaptive problem solving strategies (i.e., disengagement, avoidance, or passive coping) are associated with greater PTSD symptom severity. That is, the lesser genocide survivors get discouraged in problem solving of their daily life situation, the higher PTSD symptoms they face.

In addition, according to the protective-protective model, one protective factor may improve the effect of another protective factor in producing positive outcomes (Brook et al., 1986; Fergus & Zimmerman, 2005). Our findings support this model, suggesting that Approach coping could be regarded as a protective factor to promote the positive effects of SMM. It has been suggested that individuals with higher in Approach coping tend to exhibit less PTSD and psychological distress symptoms in that they can utilize personal psychological resources effectively to alleviate the adverse impacts of stressful events and situations (Tan, Krishnan, & Lee, 2017).

The Moderating Function of Avoidant coping

Our findings indicated that there was a strong negative effect between SMM and PTSD re-experiencing symptoms in genocide survivors with low level in stress mindsets that they reported using more avoidance coping strategies which was related to increased PTSD symptoms. Some research has demonstrated general problem avoidance coping among abuse survivors (e.g.,Leitenberg, Gibson, & Novy, 2004; Swan & Snow, 2003) and found that women who were exposed to greater levels of intimate partner abuse also report greater general problem avoidance coping(Sullivan, Meese, Swan, Mazure, & Snow, 2005). Not only is general problem avoidance coping associated with PTSD severity among IPV survivors (Street, Gibson, & Holohan, 2005), this form of coping following an abusive relationship was found to predict IPV(intimate partner violence)-related PTSD one year later (Krause, Kaltman, Goodman, & Dutton, 2008).

Limitations

Firstly, due to the cross-sectional design, the findings of the present study can not be used to establish formal causal relationships or to determine the direction of causality. Secondly, the actual prevalence of PTSD may be higher than the results reported here, because it was too emotionally changeable for genocide survivors to talk about the bereavement and some genocide survivors who still can not accept what happened to them. Finally, this study focused only on associations among stress mindset, perceived stress, PTSD symptoms, and coping strategies. Further investigation at least four years later is needed to explore some other predictors responsible for the prevalence of PTSD symptoms in genocide survivors, such as the personality of the survivors, the cognition and so on (Lee et al., 2014). Longitudinal studies are needed to validate our findings.

Conclusions

Losing parents, children, relatives and friends is a particularly traumatic and heartbreaking event for genocide survivors, which is a grievous and unique problem in Rwanda resulting from the 1994 genocide

against Tutsi. Perceived stress partly mediated the relationship between stress mindset and PTSD symptoms in Rwandan genocide survivors. The interventions of mindsets and perceived stress and coping strategies should be included in PTSD prevention. More assistance should be directed to improve the mental health of genocide survivors in Rwanda. Additionally, the prevention for genocide survivors needs to focus more on more than 36years old as they are those ones affected more. Considering the number of genocide survivors and their mental health impairment, more mental health interventions and culturally-sensitive psychological assistance should be directed to survivors in Rwanda.

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Names: *Pièrre IYAMUREMYE*

Tel: +18886130793

Email: Pierriyamuremye8@gmail.com

PIERRE IYAMUREMYE is an Educator from Rwanda, and a graduate of University of Rwanda College of Education. He holds a Bachelor of Education(Hons) in English Education (2015). A graduate of Liaoning University with a Diploma in Chinese language study (2018) and currently a graduate student of Applied Psychology of Guizhou Normal University, China (2022).

After earning his Bachelor of Education (Hons) in English Education, he entered into Education industry to explore his desires and passion for Teaching and Learning . He taught for two years as a senior Secondary class Teacher.

Mr. PIERRE IYAMUREMYE is currently a researcher with interest in Applied Psychology at Guizhou Normal University.

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